

SAC-Based Distributed Optimal Control of Generation Cost in DC Microgrids

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Abstract—Optimal Generation Cost (OGC) is a key factor in the efficient operation of DC Microgrid (DC MG). OGC in Microgrids (MGs) is influenced by the Optimal Power Flow (OPF) problem, which is inherently non-linear and non-convex. Traditional methods, often operating on different time scales, struggle with real-time implementation and rely on precise system models, making them vulnerable to uncertainties and disturbances. Recent advances in Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) offer alternative data-driven methods to handle these complexities. This study proposes a distributed optimal control framework for DC MGs using the Multi-Agent Soft Actor-Critic (MASAC) algorithm. The approach learns optimal control policies without requiring accurate system models, enabling Soft Actor-Critic (SAC) agents to interact continuously with the MG environment. Simulation results demonstrate that the MASAC-based controller outperforms previous methods, such as the Twin Delayed Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (TD3) algorithm, achieving lower generation costs and improved performance under uncertainties.

Index Terms—Cost Optimization, DC Microgrids, Distributed Control, Multi-agent Systems, Optimal Power Flow, Reinforcement Learning, Soft Actor-Critic.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background and Motivation

Recent advancements in distributed generation (DG) have greatly influenced the growth and adoption of microgrids (MGs), making them more viable and attractive for power distribution systems. Unlike traditional AC MGs, DC MGs eliminate frequency synchronization, reactive power flow, and power quality issues. They offer improved efficiency due to fewer stages of power conversion and facilitate the integration of renewable energy sources and storage technologies [1]. MGs can operate in two modes: islanded and grid-connected. Some MGs operate permanently in islanded mode due to their lack of access to a main grid, particularly in shipboards, aircrafts, and automotive systems [2]. Operating in islanded mode requires careful attention to the limitations of DGs to ensure that MG stability is maintained while adequately meeting local load demands without relying on external power sources [3]. Furthermore, reducing the generation costs associated with DGs is essential to achieving economic dispatch. Minimizing the generation costs of DGs while satisfying

the operational constraints of the DC MG can be expressed as the optimal power flow (OPF) problem [4]. Due to the interaction between bus voltages and power generation, the OPF problems lead to non-convex and nonlinear optimization, which is computationally intensive [5]. Typically, There are three strategies to deal with the computational complexity associated with OPF: 1) approximating the OPF equations through linearization methods; 2) identifying local optima of the OPF problem; and 3) convexifying the constraints imposed by nonlinear power flow equations [6].

B. Literature Review

In recent years, numerous studies have diligently worked toward addressing the optimal generation control for DC MGs. For instance Moayedi and Davoudi [7] proposed a convex optimization strategy for simultaneous voltage regulation and cost minimization in islanded DC MG using consensus-based algorithms. In [8], the economic operation of Islanded DC MG is achieved by using a consensus algorithm that calculates the generation cost of the individual and neighboring units and reroutes the power flow accordingly. Sousa et al. [9] present a globally convergent optimization algorithm combining trust-region and interior-point methods for solving nonlinear OPF problems. Their approach utilizes an infinity-norm trust-region to enhance robustness and ensure convergence from arbitrary initial points. However, this method involves linearizing, potentially limiting its effectiveness. The aforementioned methods rely on assumptions, such as using simplified models of the MG, which can lead to significant discrepancies between their solutions and the optimal solution [10]. Besides, conventional DC MG control schemes typically operate optimization and real-time control at different time scales. Therefore, even a minor disturbance can cause deviations in bus voltages and output currents from their optimal operating points [11]. To effectively tackle the challenges mentioned, it is crucial to develop a real-time optimal control strategy that is less dependent on the MG model and approximations regarding the operational constraints. Deep reinforcement learning (DRL) is a groundbreaking solution for tackling the challenges posed by nonlinearity and non-convexity in optimal control problems. Using a model-free

approach, DRL significantly reduces reliance on system’s model, making it a more adaptable and efficient choice for highly uncertain systems [12]. In recent years, DRL has proven to be highly effective in addressing optimal control problems within DC MGs [13]. The integration of DGs is one of the primary goals of the microgrids, but it has always been a control challenge. Although centralized control architectures can manage such systems, they often suffer from limited scalability and vulnerability to single points of failure. Recent advances in Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) offer solutions to these challenges, mainly through distributed cooperative control [14]. Distributed control allows agents to communicate and coordinate with their neighbors, enabling them to work together to optimize performance toward overall goals. This cooperative framework makes distributed control particularly effective for the unknown dynamics of MGs [15]. Current research combines MAS with deep reinforcement learning (DRL) to enhance resilience against system failures, leading to the development of Multi-Agent Deep Reinforcement Learning (MADRL). [16] introduces a novel approach using MADRL, where each building operates as an independent agent. This framework is designed to support demand response strategies for systems such as Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems. By employing an actor-critic model with a shared attention mechanism, the system enables efficient real-time coordination among grid-interactive buildings. [17] introduced a Multi-Agent Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (MADDPG) approach to address the Autonomous Voltage Control (AVC) problem, resulting in a multi-agent AVC algorithm. The method leverages centralized training and decentralized execution to improve control effectiveness. Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) algorithm [18] has limitations, such as overestimation bias and high variance in Q-value estimates, which can disrupt stable learning in continuous control tasks. The Twin Delayed Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (TD3) [19] algorithm was developed to enhance the DDPG method. It employs an off-policy actor-critic framework that approximates two Q-value functions. By using the lower of these two approximations to determine the Q-value, TD3 effectively reduces overestimation bias, leading to improved performance. [20] proposed a data-driven and model-based MADRL voltage control method based on TD3 agents to manage distribution networks with high photovoltaic penetration. Unlike traditional control schemes, the approach minimizes active and reactive power adjustment costs while enhancing voltage regulation. Fan et al. proposed a TD3-based MADRL framework for the optimal generation cost problem in DC MGs [21]. While the TD3-based framework introduced in [21] performs better than DDPG, it is highly sensitive to the choice of hyperparameters, requiring extensive tuning. Moreover, the initialized experience replay buffer introduced is computationally demanding. Additionally, TD3 lacks an inherent mechanism for efficient exploration, as it relies on deterministic policies with added noise, which can be suboptimal in complex dynamic environments. To overcome some of the limitations inherent in deterministic policy algorithms like

TD3, the Soft Actor-Critic (SAC) algorithm was introduced in [22] as a model-free, off-policy reinforcement learning method based on the maximum entropy framework. SAC improves exploration and learning stability by optimizing a stochastic policy while maximizing expected return and policy entropy. This encourages diverse behaviors and helps avoid premature convergence to suboptimal policies. Compared to TD3, SAC better balances exploration and exploitation and is more robust to hyperparameter variations. Its design makes it particularly effective for high-dimensional, continuous control tasks and multi-agent environments [23].

C. Contribution of This Paper

The main contributions of the paper can be summarized as follows:

1) *MADRL Distributed Control*: A MASAC DRL distributed control framework has been proposed that adapts more effectively to dynamic environments and potential failures than the TD3-based controller, ultimately enhancing system performance and resilience.

2) *Efficient Data Sampling Method*: The MASAC algorithm provides efficient data sampling, eliminating the need for initial experience buffers while dynamically balancing exploration and exploitation.

3) *Stability and Cost Reduction*: Using the MASAC framework results in faster convergence to stable voltage levels with minimal overshoot, enhancing system stability under sudden and gradual load fluctuations. Additionally, SAC outperforms TD3 regarding cost efficiency by achieving lower steady-state generation costs.

II. PRELIMINARY CONCEPTS

This section covers the graph theory fundamentals supporting the proposed multi-agent DRL framework, followed by the generation cost optimization problem.

A. Graph Theory

The communication graph of a MAS can be described as an undirected graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$, where $\mathcal{V} = \{\mathcal{V}_1, \dots, \mathcal{V}_N\}$ represents the set of \mathcal{N} agents (nodes), and \mathcal{E} denotes the set of edges of this graph. Each element of \mathcal{E} can be represented $(\mathcal{V}_i, \mathcal{V}_j)$ which describes an edge from \mathcal{V}_i to \mathcal{V}_j . Furthermore, the set of (in-) neighbors of a node \mathcal{V}_i is $\mathcal{N}_i = \{\mathcal{V}_j : (\mathcal{V}_j, \mathcal{V}_i) \in \mathcal{E}\}$, i.e., the set of nodes with edges incoming to \mathcal{V}_i . \mathcal{N}_i is the set of all nodes in which the \mathcal{V}_i receives information from them; the weights $\alpha_{ij} > 0$ are selected to model the strength of the interaction between nodes. As we are using an undirected communication graph for our model, the $\alpha_{ij} = \alpha_{ji}$.

B. Generation Cost Optimization Problem

This section presents the optimization problem for minimizing total generation costs within the DGs of the studied DC MG, as follows [24]:

$$f(P) = \sum_{i=1}^n f_i(P_i) \quad (1)$$

Where $P_i \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $i \in \mathcal{V}$, $f_i(P_i)$ is the quadratic generation cost function of the i th DG in the MG, and is formulated as:

$$f_i(P_i) = a_i P_i^2 + b_i P_i + c_i, \quad i \in \mathcal{V} \quad (2)$$

Where $a_i, b_i, c_i \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $i \in \mathcal{V}$ are the individual cost coefficients; Additionally, the generated power level of the DG i is bounded by generation capacity constraints, which are expressed as $\underline{P}_i \leq P_i \leq \overline{P}_i$ where $\underline{P}_i \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and $\overline{P}_i \in \mathbb{R}^+$, for $i \in \mathcal{V}$ are the lower and upper bounds of DG i 's generation capacity, respectively. To enhance system operation reliability, the bus voltage should also be regulated, which is expressed as $\underline{V}_i \leq V_i \leq \overline{V}_i$, where \underline{V}_i and \overline{V}_i denote the lower and upper bounds of the bus i 's voltage.

Moreover, for each bus $i \in \mathcal{V}$, let P_i^d represent the load demand at the bus i from its neighbors. In this way, the bus (node) i is connected to its neighbor j via a conductance line, and the current I_{ij} is defined as follows:

$$I_{ij} = (V_i - V_j) g_{ij} \quad (3)$$

Then, the power P_{ij} transferred from node i to node j is:

$$P_{ij} = V_i I_{ij} = V_i (V_i - V_j) g_{ij} \quad (4)$$

Consequently, the power balance at a given node is:

$$P_{ij} - P_i^d = V_i \sum_{k:k \in \mathcal{N}_i} (V_i - V_j) g_{ij} \quad (5)$$

where \mathcal{N}_i represents the set of buses directly connected to bus i , and g_{ij} denotes the admittance of the transmission line connecting bus i to bus j .

Hence, to achieve optimal operation of DC microgrids, the problem involves minimizing the overall generation cost $f(P)$, adhering to generation constraints, and ensuring bounded voltage regulation, and can be formulated as the following optimal control problem:

$$\text{minimize } f(P) = \sum_{i=1}^n f_i(P_i) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{s.t. } P_{ij} = V_i I_{ij} = V_i (V_i - V_j) g_{ij} \quad (6a)$$

$$\underline{P}_i \leq P_i \leq \overline{P}_i \quad (6b)$$

$$\underline{V}_i \leq V_i \leq \overline{V}_i \quad (6c)$$

Which $P = [P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n]^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the DGs' output powers; $V = [V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n]^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the bus voltages.

It is essential to emphasize that the OPF problem (6) presents a non-convex and non-linear optimization challenge, mainly due to its constraints and the relationship between the generated power P and bus voltage V [25].

III. MASAC-BASED DRL OPTIMAL CONTROL

To implement the MASAC-based DRL optimal control framework, the studied DC MG should be modeled as sub-networks using graph theory. Practically, each agent is assigned based on the buses' locations or electrical distances within the power system. Consequently, local controllers are designated to achieve specific local control objectives, such

as voltage regulation and power-sharing. Within the Markov decision process (MDP), the state S , action A , and reward R , the proposed optimal control problem is defined as follows [26]:

1) *State*: The local DRL agent i must be capable of observing the generated power P_i of DG i , the voltage V_i and output current I_i of bus i , as well as information from its neighboring agents. At each time step t , the agent's environment state space should produce a set of states as follows:

$$S_t^i = [V_t^i, V_t^j, P_t^i, P_t^j, I_t^i, I_t^j], \{i, j\} \in \mathcal{V} \quad (7)$$

2) *Action*: The agent's action space corresponds to the control signal of the proposed DRL controller. Given the environment dynamics (13), control signal determines the value of the V_{S_i} which is the output voltage of the i th DG's connected converter.

3) *Reward*: To minimize (6), the objective functions and operational constraints must be included in the agent's reward function, which is formulated as follows:

$$r = w \left(\sum_{i=1}^n (r_i)^3 + \zeta \right) - \beta, i \in \mathcal{V} \quad (8)$$

where w is the weight of the overall negative generation cost, $\zeta \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is a constant learning parameter, and β is the penalty term applied when the operational boundaries are not maintained during the training process, representing the individual bus voltage bound. Additionally, $r_i = -f_i(P_i)$ represents the negative local generation cost.

Using the MASAC algorithm, each agent benefits from entropy regularization, encouraging diverse exploration and enhancing learning stability. In a distributed manner, each local SAC agent is trained using information from itself and its neighbors, ensuring efficient policy learning, as depicted in Fig.2. The SAC algorithm utilizes two Q-value networks, Q_{ϕ_1} and Q_{ϕ_2} , to minimize overestimation bias and improve learning stability. Target critic networks denoted as $Q_{\phi_{\text{target},1}}$ and $Q_{\phi_{\text{target},2}}$, compute the target values for the Bellman backup, ensuring stable updates during training. For agent i , the Q-value estimation is defined as follows:

$$y^i(r_n^i, s_{n+1}^i, d_n^i) = r_n^i + \gamma (1 - d_n^i) \left(\min_{m=1,2} Q_{\phi_{\text{target},m}}^i(s_{n+1}^i, \tilde{u}_{n+1}^{\theta^i}(s_{n+1}^i, \Psi^i)) - \alpha \log \pi_{\theta^i}(\tilde{u}_{n+1}^{\theta^i}(s_{n+1}^i, \Psi^i) | s_{n+1}^i) \right) \quad (9)$$

In this context, s_n^i and s_{n+1}^i denote the observed states of agent i at the n^{th} and $(n+1)^{\text{th}}$ samples. The signal d_n^i indicates the end of the sampling process, while r_n^i is the calculated reward for the n^{th} sample. Additionally, \tilde{u}_{θ^i} represents the desired control action for the next time step. Thus, the control action is:

$$\tilde{u}_{n+1}^{\theta^i}(s_{n+1}^i, \Psi^i) = \text{sigmoid}(\mu_{\theta^i}(s_{n+1}^i) + \sigma_{\theta^i}(s_{n+1}^i) \odot \Psi^i), \Psi^i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I) \quad (10)$$

Algorithm 1 MASAC-Based Distributed Optimal Control Training Algorithm

- 1: Establish the initial states for the DC microgrid environment
- 2: Each agent $i \in \mathcal{N}$ observes the local and neighbors' state s_0^i , executes the local action u_0^i
- 3: For each agent i , set the parameters for the stochastic policy network θ^i and the Q-function networks ϕ_1^i and ϕ_2^i
- 4: **Initialization**
- 5: Initialize the policy and Q-function networks' parameters ϕ_1^i , ϕ_2^i , and θ^i
- 6: Initialize the target Q-function networks' parameters: $\phi_{\text{targ},1}^i \leftarrow \phi_1^i$, $\phi_{\text{targ},2}^i \leftarrow \phi_2^i$
- 7: **repeat**
- 8: **for** each episode from 1 to N_{episodes} **do**
- 9: Agent i observes the agent i 's state s_t^i
- 10: **for** $t = 1$ to N_{steps} **do**
- 11: The agent i 's control action is generated
$$\tilde{u}_{t+1}^i = \text{sigmoid}(\mu_{\theta^i}(s_t^i) + \sigma_{\theta^i}(s_t^i) \odot \Psi^i), \Psi^i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$$
- 12: The action for control u_t^i is deployed in the targeted environment
- 13: The instant calculated reward r_t^i and termination signal d_t^i are generated, and the next state s_{t+1}^i is received
- 14: The transition $(s_t^i, u_t^i, r_t^i, d_t^i, s_{t+1}^i)$ is stored in the replay buffer D
- 15: **if** $t > t_{\text{start}}$ **then**
- 16: Sample a random mini-batch B of transitions $(s_n^i, u_n^i, r_n^i, d_n^i, s_{n+1}^i)$ from D
- 17: Compute target Q-values for the next state using target networks and entropy term
$$y^i(r_n^i, s_{n+1}^i, d_n^i) = r_n^i + \gamma(1 - d_n^i) \left(\min_{m=1,2} Q_{\phi_{\text{targ},m}^i}(s_{n+1}^i, \tilde{u}_{n+1}^{\theta^i}(s_{n+1}^i, \Psi^i)) - \alpha \log \pi_{\theta^i}(\tilde{u}_{n+1}^{\theta^i}(s_{n+1}^i, \Psi^i) | s_{n+1}^i) \right)$$
- 18: Update the Q-function networks by minimizing the loss:
$$\mathcal{L}(\phi_m^i) = \frac{1}{|B|} \sum_{(s_n^i, u_n^i, r_n^i, d_n^i, s_{n+1}^i) \in B} (Q_{\phi_m^i}(s_n^i, u_n^i) - y^i(r_n^i, s_{n+1}^i, d_n^i))^2$$
- 19: Update the policy network using the sampled policy gradient:
$$J(\theta^i) \approx \mathbb{E}_{s_n^i \in B} \left(\min_{m=1,2} Q_{\phi_m^i}(s_n^i, \tilde{u}_{\theta^i}(s_n^i, \Psi^i)) - \alpha \log \pi_{\theta^i}(\tilde{u}_{\theta^i}(s_n^i, \Psi^i) | s_n^i) \right)$$
- 20: Softly update the target networks:
$$\phi_{\text{targ},m}^i \leftarrow \rho \phi_m^i + (1 - \rho) \phi_{\text{targ},m}^i, \text{ for } m = 1, 2$$
- 21: **end if**
- 22: **if** $d_t^i = 1$ **then**
- 23: Terminate the current episode and reset the environment to the initial state.
- 24: **end if**
- 25: **end for**
- 26: **end for**
- 27: **until** Convergence

Algorithm 2 MASAC-Based Distributed Optimal Control Real-Time Execution Algorithm

- 1: Set the well-trained parameters of the policy network for each distributed local agent i
 - 2: **for** each time step $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ **do**
 - 3: Obtain the states from the local environment and neighbors s_t
 - 4: Calculate the action a_t or u_t according to the well-strained policy
 - 5: Execute the calculated action V_{s^i} as the control for the converter i 's output voltage.
 - 6: **end for**
-

In equation (10), $\mu_{\theta^i}(s_{n+1}^i)$ is the function approximator for the mean of the next action's probabilistic distribution, while $\sigma_{\theta^i}(s_{n+1}^i)$ approximates its standard deviation. The noise vector Ψ^i , sampled from a standard normal distribution, introduces stochasticity in action selection, while the sigmoid function ensures actions remain within 0 and 1. The Q-value network loss function is defined as follows: The loss function for the Q-value networks is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}(\phi_m^i) = \nabla_{\phi_m^i} \frac{1}{|B|} \sum_{(s_n^i, u_n^i, r_n^i, s_{n+1}^i, d_n^i) \in B} \left(Q_{\phi_m^i}^i(s_n^i, u_n^i) - y^i(r_n^i, s_{n+1}^i, d_n^i) \right)^2 \quad (11)$$

Additionally, the actor parameters for agent i can be calculated using gradient ascent. This leads to the following policy gradient approach:

$$\nabla_{\theta^i} \frac{1}{|B|} \sum_{s_n^i \in B} \left(\min_{m=1,2} Q_{\phi_m^i}^i(s_n^i, \tilde{u}_n^{\theta^i}(s_n^i)) - \alpha \log \pi_{\theta^i}^i(\tilde{u}_n^{\theta^i}(s_n^i) | s_n^i) \right) \quad (12)$$

The DRL algorithm focuses on reward design and exploration techniques. The training process for agent i in the proposed distributed DRL optimal control method is outlined in Algorithm 1 and Fig.1.

Fig. 1: DRL agent structure.

IV. MASAC-BASED DRL OPTIMAL CONTROL IMPLEMENTATION

As shown in Fig.2, the MASAC-based optimal control algorithm is integrated into a DC microgrid with multiple buses. The parameters for the studied DC MG are listed in Table.I. Solid lines represent electrical connections, while dashed lines indicate communication between local DRL agents at each bus. The system dynamics arise from DG models, as shown in Fig.3. Therefore, the dynamics of the system can be expressed as below:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{V}_i = \frac{1}{C_i} (I_{Si} - I_i) \\ \dot{I}_{Si} = \frac{1}{L_i} (V_{Si} - I_{Si}R_i - V_i) \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

TABLE I: DC Microgrid Parameters

Quantity	Value
$g_{12}, g_{13}, g_{24}, g_{34} (p.u.)$	4.608
$\bar{P}_1, \bar{P}_2, P_3, \bar{P}_4 (p.u.)$	1.0
$P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4 (p.u.)$	0.0
$\bar{V}_1, \bar{V}_2, \bar{V}_3, \bar{V}_4 (p.u.)$	1.05
$V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4 (p.u.)$	0.95
$I_{L_i} (A)$	20.0, 10.0, 10.0, 5.0
$a_i (p.u.)$	0.1085, 0.1085, 0.1085, 0.1085
$b_i (p.u.)$	0.0832, 0.0260, 0.0832, 0.0260
$C_i (p.u.)$	0.008, 0.006, 0.008, 0.006
$R_i (\Omega)$	0.2, 0.1, 0.1, 0.2
$L_i (mH)$	2.0, 2.0, 1.5, 2.0
$C_i (\mu F)$	250, 200, 250, 200
Nominal Bus Voltage (V)	48
Nominal Power Rate (W)	1000

Fig. 2: Topology of the studied DC MG.

Fig. 3: The model of the i th DG.

V. RESULTS

A. Learning Performance

The Hyperparameters of the MASAC framework are presented in Table.II and are uniform across all agents. The graph in Fig.4 shows the reward trajectory over 1,400 training episodes for the SAC agents, totaling about 1.2 million learning steps. It reveals a consistent increase in cumulative rewards, indicating convergence and gradual progress toward optimal solutions. The smooth curve at the end suggests that the learning process has stabilized, resulting in reliable performance by the agents in control tasks. Fig.5 shows the Q-value trajectories for four SAC agents during training, covering approximately 300,000 learning steps with values averaged every 800 steps for clarity. Initially, all agents rapidly in-

TABLE II: Hyperparameters for MASAC Agents

Parameters	Values
Batch Size	500
Replay Buffer Size	300,000
Discount Factor	0.98
Target Smooth Factor	0.005
Learning Rate of Critic 1	0.0015
Learning Rate of Critic 2	0.01
Target entropy value	-1
Initial entropy component weight	1
Entropy Coefficient Learning Rate	0.0003
Reward Weight	0.35937
Reward Constant	1000
Boundary Penalty	20

Fig. 4: The evolution of the sum of rewards during training.

crease their Q-values, indicating effective learning. As training continues, the Q-values stabilize and converge towards higher values, demonstrating successful policy optimization by the SAC agents.

Fig. 5: The evolution of the Q-Values during training.

B. Control Performance of MASAC-Based DRL Controller

This section compares the control performance of the proposed distributed MASAC-based DRL controller with the TD3 optimal controller from [21], ensuring a fair evaluation

TABLE III: Dynamic Load Conditions

Time(s)	$I_{L_1}(A)$	$I_{L_2}(A)$	$I_{L_3}(A)$	$I_{L_4}(A)$
1.0 - 2.5	20.0	10.0	10.0	5.0
2.5 - 4.25	25.0	5.0	10.0	15.0
4.25 - 6.0	20.0	15.0	5.0	10.0

under identical conditions. A dynamic load profile for the DC microgrid is provided to evaluate the proposed controller, as shown in Table III. Step load changes occur at 1 second, while loads change with specific ramp rates at 2.5 and 4.25 seconds.

Fig. 6: Comparison of bus voltages' trajectories with the proposed DRL controller.

Fig. 7: Comparison of the generation costs.

The adaptability of the controllers to changing load conditions was tested with step and ramp load demands. Fig.6 shows the bus voltage trajectories for a representative bus controlled by the SAC and TD3 controllers. The SAC controller reached stable voltage levels faster and maintained them more consistently within the safe operational range than the TD3 controller, demonstrating superior stability with reduced overshoot and quicker stabilization. Fig.7 compares the total

costs of DGs. The results show that the SAC controller has lower generation costs than the TD3 controller and adapts better to load changes, resulting in reduced operational costs.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a distributed MASAC-based optimal generation control approach for DC microgrids. Exploiting the model-free nature of SAC, the proposed controller effectively addresses the non-linear, non-convex optimization challenges in DC microgrid operation. Testing under various dynamic load conditions demonstrated that the SAC controller consistently outperformed the TD3-based controller by achieving lower steady-state generation costs, faster voltage stabilization, and improved robustness in maintaining operational stability. Additionally, its efficiency in learning without relying on an initial experience buffer underscores its suitability for real-time control applications. The proposed SAC controller provides a reliable and efficient solution for dynamic load management in DC microgrids. While the MASAC algorithm demonstrates enhanced performance through reduced generation costs and faster voltage stabilization, its effectiveness depends heavily on robust communication between agents, an aspect that may be compromised by network delays and data losses in real-world applications. Additionally, training multiple SAC agents simultaneously may limit scalability in larger microgrid systems. Therefore, more real-world validation is needed to ensure its reliability under unpredictable conditions.

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